

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

CONGRESS
OF THE SERBIAN GENETIC SOCIETY

2019 | October
13–17
VRNJAČKA BANJA • SERBIA

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Abstracts of the 6th CONGRESS OF THE SERBIAN GENETIC SOCIETY

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VRNJAČKA BANJA · SERBIA

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WELCOME TO VI CONGRESS OF THE SERBIAN GENETIC SOCIETY!

Dear colleagues,

Welcome to the 6th Congress of the Serbian Genetic Society. The Serbian Genetic Society (SGS) has been founded in 1968 and the first Congress organized by the SGS was held in 1994 in Vrnjacka Banja. Since then, the Congress of Serbian Genetic Society is held every five years. Over the past years, the Congress has grown from a national to an international meeting.

The experience of the past meetings motivated our efforts to continue with this series with a clear tendency to strengthen the scientific connections among researchers from different European countries.

The Congress will focus on the most recent advances in genetics and on wide range of topics organized in 9 sessions and two workshops. Many of the presentations will be in lecture-like settings, but we hope that there will also be ample opportunities for informal interaction outside the scheduled sessions.

The successful organization of the Congress has required the talents, dedication and time of many members of the Scientific and Organizing committees and strong support from our sponsors. I hope that you will find the Congress both pleasant and valuable, and also enjoy the cultural and natural beauty of Vrnjacka Banja.

Yours sincerely,

Branka Vasiljevic
 President of the Serbian Genetic Society

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Plenary lectures

VI CONGRESS OF THE SERBIAN GENETIC SOCIETY

02 – 03 Invited lecture

CLINICAL AND GENETIC ASPECTS
OF OVERGROWTH SPECTRUM SYNDROMES

Ivana Kavčan

Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad,
Institute for Children and Youth Health Care of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbiaivana.kavcan@mf.uns.ac.rs

Overgrowth spectrum syndromes are heterogeneous group of diseases that are characterized by excessive tissue development with manifestations often overlapping each other. It could be generalized or segmental, with prenatal or postnatal onset, with or without intellectual impairment, hereditary or non-hereditary condition, associated or not associated with increased risk for tumors and vascular malformations. Most of them are rare and have a genetic basis, others are rare disorders and have uncertain etiology. Some of them are recognized as a part of PROS disorders that can be caused due to mutations in the somatic and germline activating pathways in PI3K/AKT/mTOR signaling, which underlie the mechanism of heterogeneous segmental overgrowth phenotypes. Careful clinical examination, imaging, and histopathology with detection of mutations, are crucial in establishing definite diagnosis. It is not always possible to detect mutations, even in cases where it exists, due to low-level somatic mosaicism. These patients should be monitored for other possible associated complications such as vascular malformations and skeletal abnormalities. In conclusion, overgrowth syndromes are important to diagnose, not just for accurate genetic counseling, but also for knowledge surrounding neoplasm surveillance and prognosis. Further screening of the genes encoding overgrowth spectrum diseases will improve molecular diagnosis and genetic counseling. Although genotype–phenotype correlation for some overgrowth syndromes is not sufficiently understood, the correlation of genetic discoveries and molecular pathways that may contribute to the clinical phenotypic expression is also important, as may lead to potential therapeutic strategies.

PIK3CA-RELATED OVERGROWTH SPECTRUM (PROS); SOMATIC MOSAICISM;
GENOTYPE-PHENOTYPE ASSOCIATION; GENETIC COUNSELING

02 – 04 Invited lecture

THE IMPORTANCE OF CORRECTLY REPORTING
DIAGNOSTIC GENETIC TEST RESULTS

Marina Đurišić

Laboratory of Medical Genetics, Mother and Child Health
Care Institute of Serbia „Dr Vukan Ćupić“, Belgrade, Serbiamarinaduriscic@gmail.com

The increasing use of genetic analyzes in routine medical practice has led to a need for improving writing and interpretation of results. This worldwide trend was also recognized by the Serbian Medical Genetics community. For that purpose we have reviewed the recommendations of various associations such as ECA (European Cytogeneticists Association), GenQA (Genomics Quality Assessment), ESHG (European Society of Human Genetics), ACGS (Association for Clinical Genetic Science), ACMG (The American College of Medical Genetics and Genomics), CF Network etc.

Every laboratory has their policies and protocols of reporting the outcome of genetic investigations to the patient. But, the report has to fulfill some requirements that are common to all. The main request is correct and appropriate nomenclature, followed by a clear written description of the genetic finding (normal or abnormal), the name of any associated syndrome/disease/prognosis, clinical interpretation, assessment/calculation of risk/recurrence, referral for genetic counselling, the basis of the test, further tests and/or information, authorizers of reports and references within reports. The aim of this lecture is to present educational resources for medical geneticists and other clinicians in order to help them provide good quality medical services.

DIAGNOSTIC GENETIC TESTING, REPORT, INTERPRETATION

**CLINICAL AND GENETIC ASPECTS
OF OVERGROWTH SPECTRUM SYNDROMES**Ivana Kavecán*Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad,
Institute for Children and Youth Health Care of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia*ivana.kavecán@mf.uns.ac.rs

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In conclusion, overgrowth syndromes are important to diagnose, not just for accurate genetic counseling, but also for knowledge surrounding neoplasm surveillance and prognosis. Further screening of the genes encoding overgrowth spectrum diseases will improve molecular diagnosis and genetic counseling. Although genotype–phenotype correlation for some overgrowth syndromes is not sufficiently understood, the correlation of genetic discoveries and molecular pathways that may contribute to the clinical phenotypic expression is also important, as may lead to potential therapeutic strategies.

PIK3CA-RELATED OVERGROWTH SPECTRUM (PROS); SOMATIC MOSAICISM;
GENOTYPE-PHENOTYPE ASSOCIATION; GENETIC COUNSELING

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